

STYLISTICS OF LEXICAL TOOLS IN ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract: Advertising text as a unit of advertising speech is an object of research for experts in various scientific fields. Stylistics of lexical means is an integral element of modern advertising text. The stylistic features of lexical tools in advertisements were analyzed in the article.

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The lexical part of linguistics has an important place in methodology. With attention to essence, the lexical layer is one of the main conditions for the correct and clear expression of thought and is second only to syntax. Therefore, the clarity and clarity of thought depends on the correct use of words. To use the word correctly, it is necessary to first understand its dictionary meaning. But this is not enough. To correctly and clearly express and understand the idea, it is necessary to have a deep knowledge of the range of meanings of words, their shades, and meaning equivalents expressed in the text. For example, the verb "to walk" is to "move" (the train was walking), "to swim" (the steamer was walking), to crawl (the snake was walking), to exist (he was walking here) in addition to "to step into motion". Means that a person who does not understand this cannot express the idea correctly and does not understand it correctly. It is impossible to learn methodology without knowing the mother tongue and all its parts perfectly. Yes, without knowing the methodology well, it is impossible to understand that our mother tongue can fully and elegantly express any thoughts, concepts, feelings, reality, etc. to the most delicate points. It is known that the opinion is expressed orally and in writing. Care and responsibility are needed in using words in both forms.

Some defects in the use of words in oral speech may not be noticed in the general idea or the listener can understand it correctly. But this cannot be done in written speech. In written speech, the nominative, denotative, and connotative meanings of each word should be taken into account. Otherwise, the idea may become vague or blurry.

Linguists M.Iminov, T.Nu'monov, and D.Bobokhonova's book "Problems of the Uzbek Language Methodology" states that the following errors may occur when choosing words in lexical methodology:

1. Misuse of words;
2. Repeating the word inappropriately;
3. Excessive use of the word;
4. Omit the word.

In our opinion, among those listed by scientists, only incorrect use and omission of the word are analyzed within the framework of lexical methodology. It is appropriate to study the rest of the word from the point of view of syntactic methodology, not lexical.

1. Misuse of the word it is characterized by not taking into account the denotative meaning of the word, using the connotative meaning as one knows. For example: *Ona va bola nosozliklarini oldini olish uchun eng muhim dori vositasi* (Foli kislota dorisi). In this sentence, instead of "health problems", the word "defects" is used, which does not correspond to the meaning of the text. In fact, the word "failure" is inappropriate for a person.

2. Uncertainty in word placement and word choice It is one of the most serious mistakes that causes mental confusion and even leads to wrong conclusions. Such errors sometimes occur as a result of "correction" by press staff trying to reduce the size of the article, and sometimes due to the author's negligence. For example: *Teri zambug'ining malakali davosi* (Ekzoderil).

Carelessness in choosing words and forming compounds is noticeable in this sentence as well. Another mistake in the use of words is to distort words and use them indiscriminately. Such a defect is found in radio and television broadcasts, as well as in the press. It is not normal to make such mistakes nowadays, when efforts are being made to improve the culture of speech, and people are demanding accuracy in their statements of opinion.

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